

Synthesis of Monoarylidene Butyrolactone and Arylnaphthalide Lignans of *Polygala chinensis*

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Condensation of ($\pm$)-3-(3', 4'-dimethoxybenzyl)-butyrolactone with piperonal, in presence of sodium methoxide, afforded a mixture of suchilactone (I) and isosuchilactone (II), the two E-/Z-isomeric monoarylidene butyrolactone lignans of *Polygala chinensis* Linn. A one-step conversion of I into justicidin-B (IV) was accomplished by NBS. NBS treatment of II, on the other hand, afforded IV and an acyclic bromo derivative (VI). VI was converted into IV and an diphyllin (V), via the diarylidene (III), on treatment with NEt_3 . Dehydrogenation of I with DDQ afforded III which was subsequently converted into a mixture of IV and V. These methods exemplify two potentially simple synthetic routes to 1-aryl-2,3-naphthalide lignans.

SUCHILACTONE (I) was previously reported in *P. chinensis* Linn. (Polygalaceae)¹ and its structure was established on the basis of chemical transformation and spectral evidence. We now report a synthesis of suchilactone and its one-step conversion into two congener 1-aryl-2, 3-naphthalide lignans, viz., justicidin-B (IV) and diphyllin (V), by NBS.

Condensation of ($\pm$)-3-(3', 4'-dimethoxybenzyl)-butyrolactone² with piperonal, in presence of sodium methoxide, followed by treatment with *HCl*, afforded a mixture of E-/Z-isomeric³ monoarylidene butyrolactone lignans, viz. suchilactone (I, E-isomer) and isosuchilactone (II, Z-isomer). These were separated by preparative layer chromatography over silica gel G.

Another aspect of this study, initially, was the evaluation of the possible role of the monoarylidene lignans of *P. chinensis* in the biogenesis of the congener aryl-naphthalide lignans. Previous reports suggested^{4,5} that diarylidenebutyrolactone derivatives could serve as a precursor of 1-aryl-2, 3-naphthalide type lignans. Accordingly, we wished to prepare the diarylidenebutyrolactone lignan (III, in two geometrical isomeric forms), corresponding to the naturally occurring monoarylidenebutyrolactone lignans (I and II) and also to investigate the role of III in the genesis of the aryl-naphthalide lignans of the titled species^{6,7}. Two routes, viz. allylic bromination followed by dehydrobromination, and dehydrogenation by DDQ, were selected for this purpose.

Interestingly, attempted allylic bromination of I gave directly justicidin-B (IV) in a high yield. Apparently, the reaction did not stop at the bromination stage but followed two further steps, cyclisation and oxidation to afford IV as the major product. Isosuchilactone (II) on treatment with NBS, on the other hand, afforded a mixture of IV and a stable bromo derivative VI. Dehydrobromination of VI with NEt_3 afforded a mixture of IV and V, via the diarylidene (III).

Dehydrogenation of I with DDQ, in anhydrous dioxane, afforded III. The diarylidene was autoxidised in acetone solution, in presence of a photosensitizer, to give a mixture of IV and V. Acetone solution of the diarylidene on keeping also suffered autoxidation to give IV and V. Such facile transformation of diarylidenes into 1-aryl-2,3-naphthalide and 1-aryl-4-hydroxy-2, 3-naphthalide lignans were previously reported^{8,9} in the literature. However, laboratory analogy for the genesis of aryl-naphthalide lignans having lactone ring in retro disposition (e. g in justicidin-C and -D) is not yet known.

Suchilactone was isomerized into isosuchilactone, in good yields, by UV irradiation of its acetone solution. The method was previously reported⁹ in the conversion of hiballactone (E-isomer) into isohiballactone (Z-isomer).

Experimental

UV spectra were recorded on a Cary 14 or Spektromon 203 spectrophotometer in methanol, PMR spectra with a Varian A-60 or 90 MHz spectrometer in CDCl_3 , and mass spectra on a MS-50 spectrometer operating at 70 ev. Column chromatography was done with silica gel (BDH, 60-120 mesh). Analytical and preparative layer chromatography (0.4 and 1 mm plates,

respectively) were carried out with silica gel G (E. Merck) using benzene-acetic acid (98:2). Spot detection was made by UV fluorescence and I_2 vapour.

Synthesis of Suchilactone (I): ($\pm$)-3-(3', 4'-dimethoxybenzyl)-butyrolactone² (0.26 g), piperonal (0.165 g), and NaOMe (0.064 g), in benzene (8 ml) were kept in a stoppered flask, at ambient temperature, for 6 days with occasional shaking. The reaction was acidified with dil. HCl and extracted with benzene (3 $\times$ 25 ml portions). The organic layer was worked up in the usual fashion and concentrated. The concentrate showed two blue fluorescent spots (under shortwave UV. lamp) on analytical TLC, R_f 0.5 and 0.55. These were separated by PLC. The component R_f 0.5, crystallized from alcohol in colourless shining needles (0.18 g), m.p. 135°; u.v.: λ_{max} nm (ϵ) 233 (ϵ 22500), 282 (ϵ 12200), 335 (ϵ 21800) nm; i.r.: ν_{max} (KBr) ν_{max}^{NaBr} 1715, 1588 cm^{-1} ; 1H n.m.r.: δ 7.3 (HC=C), 7.2-6.6 (6H, Ar-H), 4.3-4.1 (lactonic -CH₂-), 4.0 (-CH-), 2.8-2.4 ppm (Ar-CH₂-). The physical and spectral properties of the synthetic compound were indistinguishable from those of suchilactone¹. Direct comparison (m.m.p., co-TLC) also supported the above identification.

Isosuchilactone (II): This compound was isolated as the less polar component, R_f 0.55, by PLC and crystallized from alcohol as colourless microcrystals (22 mg), m.p. 133-135°; λ_{max} nm (ϵ) 233 (16700), 82 (12345), 333 (16780); ν_{max} 1735, 1642 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.7-6.8 (6H, Ar-H) (the signal from the vinyl proton was buried in the aromatic region) 4.4-3.9 (lactonic -CH₂-), 3.5 (-CH-), 3.0-2.4 (Ar-CH₂-).

Conversion of suchilactone into justicidin-B by NBS: Suchilactone (0.22 g) and NBS (0.2 g), in anhydrous CCl₄ (20 ml), were refluxed (1 hr) during which time the reaction mixture first turned brown and finally became colourless. Succinimide formed was removed by filtration. The filtrate was evaporated and the residue crystallized from alcohol as colourless needles (0.164 g), m.p. 246-248°. The m.p., m.m.p., R_f value, UV, and PMR spectra of the compound were identical with those of justicidin-B isolated *P. chinensis*^{10,11}.

Conversion of suchilactone into diarylidene (III) by DDQ: Suchilactone (0.51 g) and DDQ (Fluka, 0.54 g), in anhydrous dioxane (A.R., BDH, 50 ml) were refluxed (18 hr). The precipitated DDQH₂ was filtered off and the filtrate was passed through a short column 10 $\times$ 1 cm). The eluate was concentrated and subjected to analytical t.l.c. It showed three major and two minor spots at R_f 0.2-0.6. One of the components, R_f 0.43, corresponded with suchilactone. The major components were separated by p.l.c. The diarylidene was obtained as the least polar component, R_f 0.65, as a yellow gummy material (0.14 g), λ_{max} 222, 230, 252, 285, 310-315 nm; ν_{max} (nujol) 1750, 1598 cm^{-1} ; m/e 366 (M⁺, 62%), 351 (17), 336 (8), 321 (5), 308 (5) (Found: C, 68.5; H, 4.7. C₂₁H₁₈O₆ requires: C, 68.8; H, 4.9%).

Transformation of III into justicidin-B and diphyllin: A solution of III (0.08 g) and Rose Bengal (10 mg), in acetone (50 ml), was kept in sunlight (24 hr.). It was filtered and the filtrate was concentrated. The concentrate showed three blue fluorescent and four iodine-positive spots on analytical t.l.c. P.l.c. of the acetone concentrate afforded diphyllin from the lowest fluorescent zone. It crystallized from CHCl₃-MeOH as colourless microcrystals (5 mg), m.p. λ_{max} 285-287°; λ_{max} 262 (35870), 269 (36460), 295 (9130), 320 (8320), 355 (5012); ν_{max} (nujol) 1710 cm^{-1} ; δ 5.34 (lactone -CH₂-), 3.98 (3H, OMe), 3.75 (3H, OMe). The physical and spectral properties were indistinguishable from those reported for diphyllin⁵.

Transformation of isosuchilactone into justicidin-B and bromoderivative VI by NBS: Isosuchilactone (0.17 g) was treated with NBS (0.182 g), in anhydrous CCl₄ (20 ml), as described before for suchilactone. The product showed two major blue fluorescent spots and a yellow spot on analytical TLC. These were separated by p.l.c. The blue fluorescent spot (under UV lamp), R_f 0.38 corresponded with justicidin-B. The bromo derivative (VI) was obtained as a yellow semi solid (28 mg), R_f 0.68 λ_{max} 230 (17360), 255 (17780), 315 (5495), 395 (3162); m/e 448, 446 (M⁺, 54%), 297 (34), 295 (55), 151 (100) (Found: C, 56.2; H, 4.4. C₂₁H₁₈O₆Br requires: C, 56.3; H, 4.2%).

Conversion of VII into justicidin-B and diphyllin by triethylamine: The above bromo derivative (25 mg) was dissolved in benzene (2 ml) and NEt₃ (0.2 ml) was added. The mixture was kept in a stoppered flask at 0° for 3 days. The solvent was evaporated and water (10 ml) was added. It was extracted with CHCl₃ (3 $\times$ 25 ml). The CHCl₃ layer was worked up in the usual fashion to remove the amine. PLC of the CHCl₃ concentrate afforded justicidin-B (4 mg) from the upper blue fluorescent zone, while the lower faint-blue fluorescent zone afforded diphyllin (8 mg).

Isomerization of suchilactone into isosuchilactone: Suchilactone (0.1 g) was dissolved in acetone (100 ml) and irradiated (12 hr) with UV light (128 watt). The light yellow solution showed two major spots on TLC. The blue fluorescent, more polar spot, R_f 0.55, corresponded with suchilactone. The less polar, non-fluorescent spot, R_f 0.62, corresponded with isosuchilactone. PLC of the mixture, using benzene-ethyl acetate (90:10) as the developer, yielded the two compounds in almost equal proportions.

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